

Risk Aversion and the Elasticity of Intertemporal Substitution among Australian Households

Owen Freestone and Robert Breunig (2020)
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Key findings

We estimate the Elasticity of Intertemporal Substitution (EIS) using panel data and household holdings of risky assets and find:

- risk aversion does not vary across the wealth distribution; and
- Australian households are well-described by the constant relative risk aversion (CRRA) model; and
- we estimate the coefficient of relative risk aversion to be in the range of 1.2 to 1.4.
- These findings can provide guidance for calibrating macroeconomic models of the Australian economy.

What we knew

- Risk aversion and the willingness of people to substitute consumption tomorrow for consumption today are central to the theory of individual decision making under uncertainty.
- Extensive research in the U.S. and Europe has estimated the degree of household risk aversion but there are now Australian studies that have focused on estimating this parameter.
- It is important to have Australian-specific estimates to make relevant policy for Australia rather than relying on estimates from other countries that may be quite different from Australia.

What we do

- We test whether risk aversion varies by wealth.
- The constant relative risk aversion (CRRA) assumption is often maintained in econometric studies and in macroeconomic models. When CRRA holds, the Elasticity of Intertemporal Substitution (EIS) can be used to identify the degree of risk aversion exhibited by households.
- We use Generalised Methods of Moments (GMM) to estimate an exact, non-linear Euler equation to identify the EIS and the coefficient of CRRA.
- We use data from the Household Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia (HILDA) survey.

What we know now

- Once we account for endogeneity in risk aversion and wealth and measurement error, risk aversion does not vary with wealth.
- We find a constant EIS of 0.74 to 0.84.
- Our GMM estimates of the CRRA parameter range from 1.2 to 1.4 across four different specifications that we estimate.

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- We check our results with an alternative estimation approach using a linearised approximation of the Euler equation. The CRRA parameter is larger using this approach, but very imprecisely estimated

What this means for economic modelling

- Models which maintain the CRRA assumption appear to be valid for Australia.
- Risk aversion in Australian households is relatively modest.
- Modellers should use a coefficient of relative risk aversion in the range of 1.2 - 1.4.

Caveats

- We use 16 years of HILDA data which is a relatively short panel for the GMM approach that we use. Analysis with a longer panel, possible in the future, would provide more precise estimates.
- We find some evidence of a negative relationship between wealth and risk aversion in some specifications, but it is never statistically significant. Risk aversion may be decreasing in wealth, but with the current length of the HILDA panel, we can not estimate this relationship with any precision. We therefore consider the CRRA assumption to be tentatively supported in our data, but future research, using more data, may find that this is not the case for Australia.
- The consumption measure that we use in the Euler equations is based upon food expenditure at home, non-food grocery items and dining out. This will only provide an unbiased estimate of the EIS if within-period preferences are homothetic. The use of food probably violates this assumption, but it is somewhat mitigated by combining grocery expenditure with going out expenditure.
- The paper has a detailed discussion of these caveats.

Where to now?

- Our estimates have interesting implications for precautionary savings. A structural life-cycle model could be used to explore the proportion of savings in Australian households that is attributable to precautionary savings. No study has examined this question in Australia.

More information

- Links to the
 - full working paper
 - the published version
- We would welcome the opportunity to present our research to your team and to discuss potential joint research projects on related or similar topics.
- Contact us at robert.breunig@anu.edu.au or owen.freestone@infrastructure.gov.au